

Dating “dated sites”: Using Correspondence Analysis to handle relative chronologies as graphs.

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1 Background

“Dated sites” in archaeology are usually not “dated sites”. In the first century AD e.g., there are only two verifiable “absolute dated sites”: Pompei (Plinius the Younger, nd, chapter LXV) and Inchtuthil (Tacitus, nd, chapters XXIX-XXXVII), of which ancient authors indicate their dates. Only parts of the “dated sites” can be set in relative relation to each other, e.g. if they belong to a group of sites within a newly occupied area or if they are part of a string of military sites related to a military campaign etc. For this purpose, we can use e.g. Allen’s interval algebra (Allen, 1983; Freksa, 1991), such as “after” or “during” (Cox et al., 2016; Cox and Little, 2022; Shaw, 2022; Thiery, 2013). However, most of the temporality of “dated sites” is usually derived from a series of historical assumptions and interpolations. Yet, the chronology of these materials is often based on material coming from the manifold of other assumed “dated sites”, thus potentially resulting in a *circulus vitiosus*. On top of that, “dated sites” are frequently given dates like “from - to”, suggesting a dating security which is actually only a probability. A methodological way out of this dilemma is possible when we enhance the assumed external dating evidence and go back to the factual occurrences and overlaps in the data from the suspected “dated sites”, since only these data are free of any temporal interpretations. This results in four different research questions:

1. How can any resulting time order of “dated sites” be comprehensively encoded and semantically modelled, e.g. by using Allen’s interval algebra and graph technologies (Cox et al., 2016; Cox and Little, 2022)?
2. How can a reproducible algorithm deal with incomplete or vague dates to fix missing start or endpoints by creating “virtual fuzzy and wobbly dates”? Are graph-based digital tools like Alligator (Thiery and Mees, 2022) or the Academic Meta Tool (AMT) (Unold et al., 2019) usable for this purpose?
3. How can results be visualised for researchers using graphs, timelines or maps (Thiery, 2013, chapter 9)?
4. Do we need a different concept of temporalities for such “dated sites”?

2 Methods and Data

As a method, the chronological assumptions used in defining “dated sites” based on archaeological find materials in the 1st century AD must be deconstructed and restricted to the occurrences and overlaps within and between “find materials” from suspected “dated sites” only, to arrive at a relative chronology. This can be achieved by using correspondence analysis and visualising the resulting dimension values on maps recalculated in Hue values. By applying the “Alligator Method” (Thiery and Mees, 2023), including the Alligator and AMT tools, we can fix missing or enhance existing start- or endpoints by adding information about the vagueness/uncertainties of the hitherto “from-to” information. The resulting relative chronology can be transferred and refined by Allen’s interval algebra and visualised in graph structures such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF).

To cover as many as possible assumed “dated sites”, the Samian (Terra Sigillata) curated in the Open Data accessible research infrastructure [Samian Research](#) with its 250’000 potter’s stamps from all over Europe is used. The paper is focused on data related to the historical southern German Limes developments and the enrollment of the Roman occupation of Britain as a cross-check for the statistically achieved relative chronologies.

Figure 1: Correspondence Analysis of “dated sites” and the occurrences of Samian potters in the Roman province Britannia. [Allard W. Mees, CC BY 4.0]

3 Findings

It turns out that it is possible to visualise historical development on maps, timelines and graph structures without using historical assumptions about individual “dated sites”. Simultaneously, this paper demonstrates that dating individual sites with the help of Samian cannot result in precise datings

as usually expected in archaeology but requires the application of a different concept of temporality. The development of the Samian consumption patterns in the progressing Southern German Limes and the enrollment of the occupation of Britain appears to be a gradual development only. Hence the precise dating ability of the “find category” Samian has been overcharged since the beginning of Samian studies in the 19th century.

Applying the before-mentioned methods, based on semantic modelling and W3C standards such as RDF (Thiery, 2018; Thiery and Unold, 2018a,b) and inspired by LOD techniques, enables the FAIRification of these data related to temporality, especially by creating interoperability and reproducibility.

References

- Allen, J. F. (1983). Maintaining knowledge about temporal intervals. <https://doi.org/10.1145/182.358434>.
- Cox, S., J. Hobbs, and F. Pan (2016). Owl-time. <https://www.w3.org/2006/time>.
- Cox, S. and C. Little (2022). Time ontology in owl. <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/#topology>.
- Freksa, C. (1991). Conceptual Neighborhood and its role in temporal and spatial reasoning.
- Plinius the Younger (n.d.). *Letters*.
- Shaw, R. (2022). Modeling and Reasoning about Incomplete, Uncertain, and Approximate Historical Dates. <https://t1p.de/5m3ow>.
- Tacitus (n.d.). *Agricola*.
- Thiery, F. (2013). Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Töpferstempel. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.774861>. Master Thesis, Fachhochschule Mainz, KM042.
- Thiery, F. (2018). Alligator vocabulary. vättern edition. <https://rgzm.github.io/alligator/vocab/>.
- Thiery, F. and A. W. Mees (2022). alligator - allen transformer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2540709>.
- Thiery, F. and A. W. Mees (2023). Alligator method. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7624871>.
- Thiery, F. and M. Unold (2018a). Academic meta tool ontology. leonard edition. <https://academic-meta-tool.xyz/ontology/>.
- Thiery, F. and M. Unold (2018b). Academic meta tool vocabulary. penny edition. <https://academic-meta-tool.xyz/vocab/>.
- Unold, M., F. Thiery, and A. Mees (2019). Academic meta tool. ein web-tool zur modellierung von vagheit. http://dx.doi.org/10.17175/sb004_004.